

Distribution and nature of soil that suppresses rice sheath blight (ShB) in the Philippines

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ShB is caused by an aerial form of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn and occurs worldwide in rice under varying cultivation. To study soil that suppresses ShB, we collected rhizosphere soil samples at heading stage in 1990 wet season from various types of ricefields at the IRRI experimental farm and at 12 other sites in the Philippines (Table 1).

We used a cork borer to make a 5-mm disc of *R. solani* mycelia from a day-old culture on potato dextrose agar. A stereomicroscope was used to record linear mycelial growth on the soil surface every 48 h for 4 d.

About 44% of the 99 soil samples suppressed *R. solani*. The rest were conducive soils. Thirty-two percent of the 65 soil samples from the IRRI experimental farm were suppressive. Linear growth of *R. solani* on the suppressive soils was about 50% or less of that on the conducive soils. This means ShB severity was less in suppressive than in conducive soils. Samples from disease-free and relatively ShB-free lowland fields appeared to be more suppressive of *R. solani*.

Table 1. Distribution of soils suppressive of or conducive to *Rhizoctonia solani* in the Philippines. IRRI, 1990 wet season.

Location	Total (no.)	Suppressive (no.)	Conductive (no.)
IRRI	65	21	44
Cavite	8	5	3
Albay	6	6	0
Camarines Sur	6	5	1
Legaspi City	2	2	0
Laguna	3	1	2
Victoria, Laguna	3	2	1
Paagahan	1	1	0
Sta. Cruz, Laguna	1	0	1
Camarines	1	0	1
Bay (Aplaya), Laguna	1	0	1
Calauan, Laguna	1	0	1
Masiit (Hoechst), Laguna	1	0	1
Total	99	43	56

Table 2. Correlation of soil properties and inhibitory effect of suppressive soil. ^a IRRI, 1990 wet season.

Factor	Data range	Average	R ²	F	Regression equation ^b
pH	4.85 - 7.72	6.45	0.34**	20.25**	Y = 44.41 - 4.43X (pH)
K ⁺	4.30 - 21.70	11.51	0.12*	5.48*	Y = 9.60 + 0.54X (K ⁺)
Ca ²⁺	38.00-124.00	89.81	0.09*	3.83*	Y = 5.66 + 0.11X (Ca ²⁺)
TEB	23.00 - 42.00	31.41	0.10*	4.25*	Y = 2.61 + 0.42X (TEB)
CEC	16.00 - 48.00	31.48	0*	0*	Y = 15.60 + 0.007X (CEC)

^a * = significant at 0.05 level. ** = significant at 0.01 level. ^b Y = mycelial length (mm/d); n = 42; the 42 soil samples were from IRRI experimental farm plots A, B, C, L, M, N, and 116-1002.

Sterilization nullified the inhibitory effect. But it could be restored in a mixture with 20% suppressive soil. Abiotic factors such as Ca²⁺, K⁺, CEC, TEB, and pH were significantly

correlated with the inhibitory effect of the suppressive soil (Table 2). It appears that soil microorganisms and some abiotic factors were associated with the suppressive effect of the soils. □

Brevennia rehi Lindinger, vector for the sheath rot (ShR) pathogen

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We attempted to establish the role of rice mealybug *Brevennia rehi* Lindinger in spreading ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams & D. Hawksw.

We collected rice mealybugs from ShR-infested fields. IR20 was inoculated using a camel's hair brush to place three bugs/sheath enclosing the young panicles. Controls were inoculated with mealybugs mass-reared in the laboratory.

Mealybugs were collected from ShR-infected sheaths, soaked in 25 ml of sterile, distilled water, and then shaken for 30 min using an electric shaker. One drop of the suspension was

microscopically examined. Mealybugs from the diseased tissues were also placed directly on potato dextrose agar medium that had been surface sterilized with 10% sodium hypochlorite for 5 min. They were then incubated at 28 ± 2 °C.

Seventy-two percent of the plants inoculated with field-collected mealybugs exhibited typical ShR symptoms within 15 d. Plants inoculated with laboratory-reared mealybugs did not produce any symptoms.

Critical examination of mealybugs collected from the diseased sheaths revealed that *S. oryzae* conidia were present on the body surface (1150 conidia/ml of water) as well as internally. Plants inoculated with the internal ShR pathogen through pin pricks inside the boot leaf exhibited ShR symptoms within 25 d. This shows that mealybugs have an important role in the spread of the ShR pathogen. □

Detection of the Philippine isolate of rice yellow dwarf (RYD) agent using DNA probes

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RYD is a serious rice disease caused by a mycoplasma-like organism (MLO). DNA probes pRYD-12 (may be chromosomal in origin) and pRYD-19 (may be extrachromosomal in origin) for RYD

MLO DNA were developed in Japan to diagnose RYD. We tested whether these two probes can detect a Philippine isolate of RYD.

DNA was extracted by homogenizing 0.1 g infected tissue in 0.9 ml 2X CTAB buffer (2% wt/vol cetyl trimethylammonium bromide, 100 mM tris-HCL, pH 8.0, 1.4 M NaCl, 20 mM Na₂ EDTA) that contained 2 μl 2-mercaptoethanol. The homogenate (0.5 ml) was incubated at 65 °C for 30 min and centrifuged at 15,000 rpm for 15 s.